

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ADVANTAGES OF USING ITC MARKET ANALYSIS TOOLS VIA CASE STUDY RESEARCH OF TEA POWDER EXPORT FROM CHINA

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the advantages of utilizing the International Trade Centre (ITC) market analysis tools through a case study of tea powder export from China to Russia. The research focuses on how ITC tools facilitate market intelligence, risk reduction, and cost optimization for exporters, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). By analyzing trade statistics, tariff rates, and market access conditions, the study highlights the growing demand for bubble tea products in Russia and identifies key opportunities and challenges in the market. The findings demonstrate that ITC tools provide a centralized platform for accessing reliable trade data, enabling exporters to make informed decisions and strategically target emerging markets. The case study underscores the importance of ITC tools in enhancing export competitiveness and supporting the development of effective trade strategies.

Keywords: International Trade Centre (ITC), market analysis tools, tea powder export, China-Russia trade, export strategies, trade barriers, market intelligence, SMEs (Small and Medium-sized Enterprises), bubble tea market, trade competitiveness.

The main challenge for exporters is the absence of reliable market intelligence, which hinders the analysis of competition and demand forecasting. This makes it significantly more difficult for exporters, especially small and medium-sized businesses, to identify new markets, countries and potential customers. Importers in turn seek to optimize their preferential trading arrangements and streamline procurement processes by seeking competitive suppliers.

The International Trade Centre conducted interviews with over 33,000 businesses in 74 countries, which revealed that the main barriers to trade are "lack of information and transparency". To address these challenges, countries require access to reliable data to make informed decisions about trade.[2]

Effective decision-making in the field of international trade is facilitated by the technical cooperation agencies of the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) and the World Trade Organization (WTO). These organizations focus on operational and entrepreneurial aspects of trade development in order to support effective decision-making. [6]

The International Trade Centre (ITC) is an organization dedicated to supporting the growth of international trade, especially in developing countries. Its goal is to help businesses and other economic actors become more competitive in global markets.

ITC provides a range of tools for market analysis, which assist users in accessing important trade-related information. These tools include a comprehensive database of trade statistics, tariff information, and free trade agreement rules. Users can also access information on market prices, export potential, regional trade patterns, and investment opportunities.

These tools cover a diverse range of geographical areas and products, and are used by over one million

users, including businesses, government agencies, and leading companies.

In our research, we aim to evaluate the usability of ITC's market analysis tools. To do so, we will analyze the main features of the platform and its functionality using the example of importing bubble tea powder from China to Russia as a case study.

We chose to study the import of bubble tea powder for several reasons. First, milk tea has become a popular product in Russia in recent years, due to an increase in interest in Asian cuisine and culture.[10] The demand for this product is steadily growing, while domestic production remains low. Imported bubble tea, in the form of powder, has become not just a drink, but also an integral part of young people's lifestyle, making it a promising product for export. Secondly, China is a leading producer of tea powder, making it an ideal trading partner for Russian importers.[9]

The average price of a cup of milk tea is 2-3 times higher in Russia (4-7\$) than in China (1-3\$), due to a number of factors. One of the main reasons for this difference is the smaller number of tea shops in Russia, as well as the reliance on imported ingredients for tea production.

In Shanghai, with a population of approximately 24.8 million people, there are approximately 1,811 tea shops. This means that there is one tea shop for every 13,727 residents. In contrast, in Moscow, with a population of around 13.15 million, there are only 555 tea shops, or one for every 23,700 people. The situation in Saint Petersburg is even more challenging, with one tea shop serving approximately 37,714 residents.

Competition in Shanghai has led to a reduction in prices, whereas in Russia, where the market is still developing, high costs represent opportunities for new entrants. The use of Chinese tea powder allows for cost

reduction: one kilogram of the product on OZON costs \$26 (40 servings at \$0.65 each), which is four to eight times cheaper than purchasing the drink in a cafe. Therefore, affordable tea powder helps consumers save on home preparation and allows businesses to offer drinks at competitive prices, strengthening their positions in a growing market.[8]

A survey among Russian consumers provided valuable insights into their preferences and attitudes towards bubble tea and tea powders. The study involved over a hundred participants from different parts of Russia. Based on the collected data, approximately 30% of respondents drink milk tea once or twice a week, 45% consume it fewer than once a month, and 25% have never tried it but expressed interest in doing so.

Regarding home preparation, the majority of participants (75%) indicated that they would be willing to make their own tea if there are financial incentives. Of these, 50% mentioned the ease of preparation as a significant factor, and 40% emphasized the importance of cost. These findings emphasize the importance of convenience and affordability for Russian consumers when choosing bubble tea products.

The utilization of the ITC platform for research into the tea powder market in Russia offers significant advantages. Firstly, it decreases the time required for searching for reliable information, providing a centralized resource for data. This is especially beneficial for small- and medium-sized exporters, who often have limited resources, and can benefit from having all essential information readily available.

Secondly, the ITC helps to minimize the risks associated with entering a new market. Through an analysis of trade statistics, tariff rates, and market conditions, exporters can better understand potential challenges they may face and prepare accordingly, reducing the likelihood of failure and increasing the chances of success.

Third, the platform helps optimize export costs by providing information on tariff rates and origin rules. This allows exporters to select the most advantageous supply conditions, making their products more competitive in the international market and reducing costs.

Additionally, the ITC supports identifying promising market opportunities and competitive advantages. For example, an analysis of demand for tea powder in Russia may reveal significant potential due to increasing interest in Asian cuisine. This enables exporters to target promising markets.

In the course of our research, we will utilize various market analysis tools provided by the International Trade Center. These tools include maps of the current trade distribution of the product, information on market availability in different countries, comparative analysis of export potential and average market prices by region, as well as summaries of import standards, tax duties, and other relevant product information.

During the research process, we will provide key summaries and tables based on the data collected.

To effectively work with the tools, it is essential to determine the Harmonized System (HS) code for our product[3]. In order to do so, we need to input the keywords corresponding to the product name into the search bar on the website. Since we plan to export bubble tea preparations, we input the word "tea". The system promptly provides us with the product category 2101 – "Extracts, essences and concentrates of coffee, tea or mate and preparations with a basis of these products or with a basis of coffee, tea or mate; roasted chicory and other roasted coffee substitutes, and extracts, essences and concentrates thereof"[1]

As we only deal with tea powder, we choose subcategory 210120 – "Extracts, essences and concentrates of tea or mate and preparations with a basis of these extracts, essences or concentrates or with a basis of tea or mate."

After determining the product's code for import, we will analyze the current market situation using the Trade Map tool. This tool provides information on trade flows, import and export volumes, as well as details of key market players. Our goal is to determine the level of interest in the target market for this product. To do so, we will add the following search criteria: "World," "Import," "by country" and the 210120 code. The system will generate a table with the relevant data:

Table 1

Importers	List of world's biggest importers of 210120 product							
	Value imported in 2023 (USD thousand)	Trade balance in 2023 (USD thousand)	Unit value (USD/unit)	Annual growth in value between 2019-2023 (%)	Annual growth in quantity between 2019-2023 (%)	Annual growth in value between 2022-2023 (%)	Share in world imports (%)	Concentration of supplying countries
World	1429129	-66144		5	2	6	100%	0.1
USA	252575	-86740	3249	8	3	1	17.7%	0.15
Netherlands	104748	67715	15914	16	8	6	7.3%	0.56
France	93960	-77975	17468	0	-5	16	6.6%	0.45
Ireland	68673	54095	11567	11	-11	0	4.8%	0.21
Germany	52926	37004	4289	12	8	24	3.7%	0.14
Canada	51714	20589	6509	-1	7	1	3.6%	0.5
Mexico	50177	-19432	23871	1	-19	11	3.5%	0.85
Korea	40907	-11379	20744	15	7	27	2.9%	0.16
Japan	37738	-17612	5630	6	35	16	2.6%	0.18
Portugal	32892	-31338	7280	24	31	20	2.3%	0.32
UK	32855	-24377	13593	15	-9	18	2.3%	0.29
Italy	31811	-17947	15563	11	8	5	2.2%	0.13
Saudi Arabia	30353	-29856		20		73	2.1%	0.69
Türkiye	26088	-15651	19339	7	0	31	1.8%	0.53
Australia	22569	-14301	15343	8	0	-17	1.6%	0.3
UAE	22063	-12043	10496	13	-6	18	1.5%	0.21
Indonesia	21029	-15918	5719	-6	0	11	1.5%	0.61
Kazakhstan	20987	-13622	8904	23	20	8	1.5%	0.23
Singapore	20489	-8373	6005	2	0	-13	1.4%	0.19
Thailand	20253	22852	13109	-2	6	-6	1.4%	0.17
Russia	19076	-16490	18290	-5	-3	1	1.3%	0.34

Let's analyze Russia's position in the global market for importing this product type. According to the data provided, Russia ranks 21st globally with a share of 1.3% in total global imports. In the year 2023, Russia imported approximately \$19 million worth of the product. It is worth noting that there is a substantial trade imbalance, with imports exceeding exports. While this is positive for exporting countries, there has been a decrease in both the value and quantity of imports since

2019, totalling -5% and -3%, respectively. A comprehensive analysis of these trends is necessary to assess their impact on our strategic planning. One positive development is the 1% increase in value between 2022 and 2023, which may indicate a renewed interest in the product market.

For a more in-depth analysis of the supply-side situation, we can utilize the same tool to investigate product exports. The following data has been obtained:

Table 2

Exporters	List of Top-5 world biggest exporters of 210120 product							
	Value exported in 2023 (USD thousand)	Trade balance in 2023 (USD thousand)	Unit value (USD/unit)	Annual growth in value between 2019-2023 (%)	Annual growth in quantity between 2019-2023 (%)	Annual growth in value between 2022-2023 (%)	Share in world exports (%)	Concentration of importing countries
World	1362985	-66144	5401	5	0	-3	100	0.05
China	175921	170249	11240	6	3	-5	12.9	0.13
Netherlands	172463	67715	33365	5	-3	-31	12.7	0.06
USA	165835	-86740	8836	-2	-2	11	12.2	0.15
Ireland	122768	54095	20957	10	-14	0	9	0.4
Germany	89930	37004	6890	5	2	-2	6.6	0.09

currently, China occupies a leading position in the global market with a market share of 12.9%. Sales amounted to approximately \$176 billion in 2023 and the trade balance stood at \$170 billion. Importing countries are not highly concentrated at the same time.

To conduct a more thorough analysis, it would be necessary to examine which countries and companies currently constitute the market for product 210120 in the Russian Federation.

Table 3

Exporters	List of 5 biggest exporters of 210120 product to Russia								
	Value imported in 2023 (USD thousand)	Trade balance 2023 (USD thousand)	Share in Russian Federation's imports (%)	Unit value (USD/unit)	Growth in imported value between 2019-2023 (% p.a.)	Growth in imported quantity between 2019-2023 (% p.a.)	Growth in imported value between 2022-2023 (% p.a.)	Ranking of partner countries in world exports	Concentration of all importing countries of partner countries
Total	19076	-16490	100	18290	-5	-3	1		
Netherlands	8820	-8820	46.2	81667	-15	-25	-4	2	0.06
Kazakhstan	6686	-4786	35	159190			168	28	0.83
China	589	-586	3.1	5663	36	32	-43	1	0.13
Malaysia	580	-580	3	1258	-3	-4	-53	8	0.1
Türkiye	464	-464	2.4	5590	217	117	55	22	0.45

Based on the data provided in the table, it can be concluded that China ranks third among countries exporting the product to Russia in terms of volume. In 2023, the export volume from China amounted to \$589 million, accounting for a market share of 3.1%.

Despite a 36% increase in the total import value from 2019 to 2021, this figure has decreased by 43% from 2022 to 2023, which may be due to a shift in trade towards Kazakhstan. Therefore, to successfully introduce this product into the market, it is necessary to develop an effective advertising strategy to attract buyers.

Currently, there are approximately 500 companies importing products in this category, compared to only 13 exporters from China. This suggests that the supply market has not yet been saturated.

The next step in the process will be to analyze the market access conditions for our product in Russia. This includes understanding tariff and non-tariff barriers, as well as certification requirements. It is essential to have a clear understanding of tariff rates and origin rules in order to optimize export costs.

To this end, we plan to use the Market Access Map tool. The tool requires us to input information about the importing and exporting countries, as well as the HS code of our product. [4] Based on this information, the tool will provide us with insights into the tariffs and regulations that apply to our product when importing from China to Russia.

According to the information provided, when importing product 210120 from China, a customs duty of 11% is applied under the MFN (Most Favored Nation) regime in Russia. However, for Kazakhstan, this duty

is zero, which is an exception. Most exporting countries, including the main supplier, the Netherlands, face the same 11% tax rate. At the moment, there are no specific trade agreements between Russia and China regarding this category of goods.

Furthermore, importing country does not impose any trade restrictions on the importation of this product. However, to export the product from our facility, it is necessary to comply with certain regulatory requirements, such as:

A210 – **Tolerance limits for residues of or contamination by certain (non-microbiological) substances;**

A220 – **Restricted use of certain substances in foods and feeds and their contact materials;**

A310 – **Labelling requirements;**

B410 – **Microbiological criteria of the final product;**

C300 – **Requirement to pass through specified port of customs, etc.**

The same set of documents must be provided by the two main competitors, Kazakhstan and the Netherlands. All necessary certificates and information are also

Let's now consider the export potential of China in the Russian market for tea extracts. To do so, we will utilize the Export Potential Mapping tool, which enables us to evaluate the demand for a product in a particular market, assisting exporters in focusing on markets with high growth potential.[5]

By inputting the product of interest and exporting country in the search bar, a map of export distribution per country is generated, along with an assessment of

unrealised potential. For Russia, this potential amounts to approximately 10 million USD, while current trade volumes are at 787 thousand USD.

These figures are derived by multiplying three components:

1. Supply: This is calculated based on the projected market share, which is defined as the percentage of exports from Country i of total exports of Product k, multiplied by the anticipated GDP growth rate for Country I compared to other exporting countries. This indicator is adjusted for global tariff benefits.

2. Demand: This is based on projections for market J, taking into account expected GDP per capita growth and the elasticity of demand for imported goods, as well as future tariff benefits and the distance between countries.

3. Ease of trading: This is calculated as the ratio of actual trade between country I and market J compared to hypothetical trade if country I had the same market share in market J as it has in global markets. A value greater than 1 indicates easier trading conditions, while a value less than 1 suggests more difficult conditions.

The potential export value of a product = supply * by demand (corrected for market access) * multiplied by the bilateral ease of trading factor.

As we can see, the market we have selected has significant potential for growth and development.

In conclusion, it can be stated that the use of ITC tools enabled us to carry out a prompt and thorough preliminary analysis of the market for bubble tea in Russia. Through the use of these tools, we were able to obtain the following data:

The target market is currently not a leading player in terms of volume of imports for this product, but there has been a steady increase in interest in this market, as confirmed by both our external analysis and the results of our survey. The exporting country is the major supplier of this product on a global scale and has significant potential for increasing its supply to the target market.

We identified Kazakhstan as a key competitor in this sector. In recent years, overall imports have increased by 168% and the exporting country has benefited from preferential tariff treatment for products in this category.

All necessary documents and certifications required for trade activities have been obtained.

It can be stated that the data collected through the tools provided by the International Trade Centre has provided us with valuable insights into key trends and trade opportunities in our selected field. Naturally, this process does not stop here; entrepreneurs also need to identify the preferences of their target audience, establish partnerships with reputable producers, and develop a product marketing strategy, among other things. However, timely access to accurate and comprehensive data can significantly impact the final business plan and the future success of the project.

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